

POLYMER AND ALIGNED CARBON NANOTUBE NANOCOMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

The excellent optoelectronic, mechanical, and thermal properties of carbon nanotubes have made them very attractive for a wide range of potential applications. However, many applications require the growth of aligned/micropatterned carbon nanotubes with or without a modified nanotube surface. We have developed a simple pyrolytic method for large-scale production of aligned carbon nanotube arrays *perpendicular* to the substrate surface. We have also used photolithographic and soft-lithographic techniques for patterning the aligned carbon nanotubes with a sub-micrometer resolution. These aligned carbon nanotube arrays can be transferred onto various substrates of particular interest (*e.g.* polymer films for organic optoelectronic devices) in either a patterned or non-patterned fashion. The well-aligned structure further allows us to prepare aligned coaxial nanowires of carbon nanotubes sheathed with polymers and to modify the surface of individual carbon nanotubes by plasma treatment. This, coupled with further chemical modification via reactions characteristic of the polymer coating and/or plasma-induced functionalities, opens up many possibilities for making novel polymer and carbon nanotube nanocomposites with desirable features for specific applications.

1. INTRODUCTION

The recent development of nanotechnology has opened up novel fundamental and applied frontiers in materials science and engineering. At the nanometer scale, the wave like properties of electrons inside matter and atomic interactions are influenced by the size of the material [1]. As a consequence, changes in the size-dependent properties (*e.g.* melting points, magnetic, optic, and electronic properties) may be observed even without any compositional change [1]. Due to the high surface-to-volume ratio associated with nanometer-sized materials, a tremendous improvement in chemical properties is also achievable through a reduction in size [1]. Besides, new phenomena, such as the confinement-induced quantization effect, could also occur when the size of materials becomes comparable to the deBroglie wavelength of charge carriers inside [1]. By creating nanostructures, therefore, it is possible to control the fundamental properties of materials through the surface/size effect. This should, in principle, allow us to develop new materials and advanced devices of desirable properties and functions for numerous applications.

Polymers offer a unique class of materials with the natural length of polymer chains and their morphologies in the bulk, lying precisely at the nanometer length scale [1]. This, together with the large number of possible conformations available to a polymer chain on a surface and/or in the bulk, indicates a considerable room for creating polymeric materials of new properties and functions even without any change in their chemical composition. On the other hand, the recent discovery of carbon nanotubes [2] has opened up a new era in material science and nanotechnology. In view of the large number of well-defined carbon-carbon single and double bonds in most carbon nanotubes, carbon nanotube at its very essence is polymeric. Having a conjugated all-carbon structure, carbon nanotubes have indeed been demonstrated to possess some similar optoelectronic characteristics to conjugated polymers. Just as conjugated polymers have widely been regarded as quasi-one-dimensional semiconductors (see, for

example: [3-5]), carbon nanotubes can be considered as quantum wires (for recent reviews, see: [6-12]). The interesting electronic and photonic properties, coupled with their unusual molecular symmetries, have made carbon nanotubes very attractive for many potential applications, including as new materials for electron field emitters in panel displays [13], single-molecular transistors [14], scanning probe microscope tips (see, for example: [15-18]), gas and electrochemical energy storage [19], catalyst and protein/DNA supports [20, 21], molecular-filtration membranes [22], and artificial muscles [23]. For most of the above-mentioned, and many other, applications, it is highly desirable to prepare aligned/micropatterned carbon nanotubes and to modify their surfaces, for example with polymers. Although a large number of solution methods have recently been reported to modify nanotube tips and sidewalls through either covalent or non-covalent chemistries [12], a simple application of the solution chemistry to the aligned carbon nanotubes, however, could cause a detrimental damage to their alignment structure. To address this problem, we have developed approaches for chemical modification of aligned carbon nanotubes whilst largely retaining their structural integrity. For instance, we have recently prepared large-scale aligned carbon nanotube arrays *perpendicular* to the substrate surface by pyrolysis of iron (II) phthalocyanine onto the pristine quartz glass plates [24]. Subsequently, we have also developed microfabrication methods for patterning the aligned carbon nanotubes with a sub-micrometer resolution and for patterned/non-patterned transferring such nanotube arrays to various other substrates of particular interest (*e.g.* polymer films for organic optoelectronic devices or metal substrates for electrochemistry) [24-28]. We have also prepared novel aligned polymer-carbon nanotube coaxial nanowires by the electrochemical (plasma) deposition of a concentric layer of an appropriate conducting (nonconducting) polymer onto the individual aligned carbon nanotubes [29], and by chemical grafting of functional polymer chains onto plasma activated aligned carbon nanotubes [30].

Polymer-nanotube hybrid composites constitute a new class of nanomaterials, which could show properties characteristic of both constituent components with potential synergetic effects. For example, nonaligned carbon nanotubes have been used as electrodes in rectifying heterojunctions with conjugated polymers, showing a significantly reduced the onset voltage for nonlinear current injection due to an enhancement of the local field at the tip of the nanotubes [31]. Likewise, light-emitting diodes (LEDs) based on conjugated polymer/carbon nanotube composites have been shown to exhibit lower current densities and better thermal stabilities than the corresponding pure polymer devices, as carbon nanotubes enhance the conductivity and act as nanometric heat sinks [32]. The use of aligned/micropatterned carbon nanotube and polymer composites could provide additional advantages. In this article, we summarize our recent work on microfabrication and chemical modification of aligned carbon nanotubes for compositing with polymers, along with some of their potential applications.

2. SYNTHESIS AND MICROPATTERNING OF ALIGNED CARBON NANOTUBES

Although carbon nanotubes synthesized by most of the common techniques, such as arc discharge and catalytic pyrolysis (for recent reviews, see: [6-12]) often exist in a randomly entangled state (Figure 1a) [32, 33], aligned carbon nanotubes have been prepared either by post-synthesis fabrication (see, for example: [34, 35]) or by synthesis-induced alignment [36]. In this regard, we have prepared aligned carbon nanotubes by pyrolyzing FePc and the detailed procedures for the aligned nanotube growth have been reported previously (see, for example: [24, 37]). Without repetition of detailed discussions on the synthesis and structural characterization, a typical SEM image of the FePc-generated aligned carbon nanotube array after having been transferred onto a gold foil is shown in Figure 1b. As can be seen, the constituent nanotubes in the perpendicularly-aligned carbon nanotube array have a fairly uniform length (20 μm). Elsewhere, we have also demonstrated that these aligned carbon nanotubes possess a well-graphitized structure with *ca.*50 concentric carbon shells and an outer diameter of *ca.*40 nm [38].

Figure 1. (a) Typical SEM images of (a) a non-aligned carbon nanotube sample and (b) aligned carbon nanotube arrays prepared by pyrolysis of FePc.

Apart from the aligned carbon nanotubes described above, certain applications (*e.g.* electron emitters for panel display, sensor arrays) may require the carbon nanotubes to be patterned onto various substrates, in a similar fashion as silicon or metals in semiconducting devices. On our further investigation of the aligned carbon nanotubes produced by the pyrolysis of FePc, we, among others [39-43], have recently developed a novel method for photolithographic generation of the perpendicularly-aligned carbon nanotube arrays with resolutions down to a micrometer scale [25]. Our method allows not only the preparation of micropatterns and substrate-free films of the perpendicularly-aligned nanotubes but also their transfer onto various substrates, including those which would otherwise not be suitable for nanotube growth at high temperatures (*e.g.* polymer films) [24]. Figure 2a shows the steps of the photolithographic process. In practice, we first photolithographically patterned a positive photoresist film of diazonaphthoquinone (DNQ)-modified cresol novolak (Scheme 1a) onto a quartz substrate. Upon UV irradiation through a photomask, the DNQ-novolak photoresist film in the exposed regions was rendered soluble in an aqueous solution of sodium hydroxide due to photogeneration of the hydrophilic indenecarboxylic acid groups from the hydrophobic DNQ via a photochemical Wolff rearrangement [44] (Scheme 1b). We then carried out the pyrolysis of FePc, leading to region-specific growth of the aligned carbon nanotubes in the UV exposed regions (Figure 2b). In this case, the photolithographically patterned photoresist film, after an appropriate carbonization process, acts as a shadow mask for the patterned growth of the aligned nanotubes. This method is fully compatible with existing photolithographic processes [45, 46].

Scheme 1 (a) Molecular structure of the DNQ-Novolak photoresist and (b) photochemical reactions of the DNQ-Novolak photoresist [25].

Figure 2. (a) Schematic representation of the micropattern formation of aligned carbon nanotubes by photolithographic process. (b) Typical SEM micrographs of patterned films of aligned nanotubes prepared by the pyrolysis of FePc onto a photolithographically prepatterned quartz substrate [25].

Subsequently, we have also used the micro-contact printing (μ CP) and micro-molding techniques to prepare micropatterns of carbon nanotubes aligned in a direction normal to the substrate surface [26]. In both cases, a thin layer of polymer film was region-specific transferred onto a quartz substrate, followed by carbonization of the polymer patterns into carbon black for region-specific growth of the aligned nanotubes in the polymer-free regions by pyrolysis of iron(II) phthalocyanine (FePc) under Ar/H₂ atmosphere at 800-1100°C, as is the case for the above-mentioned photolithographic patterning.

As can be seen from above discussion, both the photolithographic and soft-lithographic patterning methods involve a tedious carbonization process prior to the aligned nanotube growth. In order to eliminate the carbonization step, we have also developed a versatile plasma method for making patterns of aligned carbon nanotubes [27]. In this case, we first polymerized certain plasma polymers in a region-specific fashion using a TEM grid as the physical mask. The highly-crosslinked structure of plasma-polymer films [47, 48] could ensure the integrity of the plasma polymer layer to be maintained, even without carbonization, at high temperatures necessary for the nanotube growth from FePc [27]. Therefore, the carbonization process involved in our previous work on photolithographic [25] and soft-lithographic [26] patterning of the aligned carbon nanotubes can be completely eliminated in the plasma patterning process. Owing to the generic nature characteristic of the plasma polymerization, many other organic vapors could also be used equally well to generate plasma polymer patterns for the patterned growth of the aligned carbon nanotubes.

As can be seen from above discussion, micropatterns of aligned nanotubes with resolutions down to a sub-micron scale, suitable for fabrication of various electronic and photonic devices, have been prepared by lithographic and/or plasma techniques. These lithographic/plasma patterning methods, coupled with the ease with which polymer chains can be chemically and/or electrochemically attached onto the carbon nanotube wall should allow the formation of the nanostructured polymer-nanotube coaxial nanowires in a patterned fashion, attractive for constructing various on-tube optoelectronic devices and sensor arrays as we shall see later.

3. POLYMER AND ALIGNED CARBON NANOTUBE NANOCOMPOSITES

3.1. PLASMA-POLYMER-COATED ALIGNED CARBON NANOTUBES

The well-aligned structure will not only make the aligned/micropatterned carbon nanotubes the ideal material for many potential applications (*e.g.* as electron field emitters in flat panel displays, membranes for molecular separation) but also allow chemical modification for each of the individual aligned carbon nanotubes whilst largely retaining their structural integrity. The latter approach should provide further opportunities for creating polymer and nanotube composite materials of new properties and functions by regulating their surface chemistry.

We have recently carried out the plasma polymerization on the aligned carbon nanotubes. The plasma-coating thickness is typically 10-30 nm, but it can be varied in a controllable fashion by changing the plasma polymerization conditions (*e.g.* treatment time) [30]. More recently, we have carried out the effect of plasma coating on the electron emission performance of the aligned carbon nanotubes.

Figure 3 I - E plots of the gold-supported aligned carbon nanotubes before and after an n -hexane plasma treatment at 250 kHz, 30 W, and monomer pressure 0.65 Torr for different treatment time.

Figure 3 show changes in the I - E curves for the gold-supported aligned carbon nanotubes upon hexane plasma treatment. As can be seen in Figure 3, hexane-plasma coating reduces the turn-on electric field E_{io} (defined as (defined as the electric field required to emit a current $I = 10 \mu\text{A}/\text{cm}^2$) [49], coupled with a concomitant increase in the emission current at a constant V . Notably, the turn-on electric field decreased from $E_{io} = 2.5 \text{ V}/\mu\text{m}$, characteristic of the pristine aligned carbon nanotubes, to $E_{io} = 1.5 \text{ V}/\mu\text{m}$ with a significant increase in the emission current at a constant V after being treated with the n -hexane plasma for 2 min. We believe that the enhanced field emission by the hexane-plasma treatment is originated from the electrical insulating of the nanotubes along their length, leading to an enhanced field focusing at the nanotube tips.

3.2. GRAFTING POLYMERS ONTO PLASMA-ACTIVATED ALIGNED CARBON NANOTUBES

On the basis of the plasma polymerization work, we have developed approaches for chemical modification of aligned carbon nanotubes by carrying out radio-frequency glow-discharge plasma treatment, and subsequent reactions characteristic of the plasma-induced surface groups [30]. For instance, we have successfully immobilized NH_2 -containing polysaccharide chains onto acetaldehyde plasma activated carbon nanotubes through the Schiff-base formation, followed by reductive stabilization of the Schiff-base linkage with sodium cyanoborohydride (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2 Grafting polysaccharide chains onto plasma activated aligned carbon nanotubes through Schiff-base formation, followed by reductive stabilization of the Schiff-base linkage with sodium cyanoborohydride [30].

The resulting amino-dextran grafted nanotube film showed zero air/water contact angles. The (acetaldehyde) plasma treated carbon nanotube film gave relatively low advancing (90°), sessile (78°), and receding (45°) air/water contact angles comparing to the advancing (155°), sessile (146°), and receding (122°) angles for an untreated sheet of aligned carbon nanotubes. The glucose units within the surface-grafted amino-dextran chains (Scheme 2) can be further converted into dialdehyde moieties by periodate oxidation [47], thereby, providing considerable

3.3. ALIGNED CARBON NANOTUBE AND CONDUCTING POLYMER COAXIAL NANOWIRES

In addition to the chemical grafting of polymer chains onto the carbon nanotube surface, we have recently used the aligned carbon nanotubes as nanoelectrodes for making novel conducting coaxial nanowires by electrochemically depositing a concentric layer of an appropriate conducting polymer uniformly onto each of the constituent aligned nanotubes to form the aligned conducting polymer coated carbon nanotube coaxial nanowires (CP-NT) [29] (Figure 4A).

Figure 4. (A) Typical SEM images of the CP-NT coaxial nanowires produced by cyclic voltammetry on the aligned carbon nanotube electrode, showing a thin layer of conducting polymer (polypyrrole) coating surrounding each of the constituent aligned carbon nanotubes. (B) Cyclic voltammograms of (a) the polyaniline-coated CP-NT coaxial nanowires and (b) the bare aligned carbon nanotubes. Measured in an aqueous solution of 1M H_2SO_4 with a scan rate of 50 mV/s [29].

The electrochemical performance of the aligned CP-NT coaxial nanowires was evaluated by carrying out cyclic voltammetry measurements. As for polyaniline films electrochemically deposited on conventional electrodes, the cyclic voltammetric response of the polyaniline coated nanotube array in an aqueous solution of 1M H_2SO_4 (Figure 4B(a)) shows oxidation peaks at 0.33 and 0.52 V (but with much higher current densities) [50]. This indicates that polyaniline films thus prepared are highly electroactive. As a control, the cyclic voltammetry measurement was also carried out on the bare aligned nanotubes under the same conditions (Figure 4B(b)). In the control experiment, only capacitive current was observed with no peak attributable to the presence of any redoxactive species.

To demonstrate the potential sensing applications for the CP-CNT coaxial nanowires, we have also immobilized glucose oxidase onto the aligned carbon nanotube substrate by electropolymerization of pyrrole in the presence of glucose oxidase [51]. The glucose oxidase-containing polypyrrole-carbon nanotube coaxial nanowires were used to monitor the concentration change of hydrogen peroxide (H_2O_2) generated from the glucose oxidation reaction by measuring the increase in the electro-oxidation current at the oxidative potential of H_2O_2 (*i.e.* the amperometric method). The amperometric response was found to be much higher than that of more conventional flat electrodes coated with glucose oxidase-containing polypyrrole films under the same conditions.

As shown in Figure 5, a linear response of the electrooxidation current to the glucose concentration was obtained for the CP-NT nanowire sensor. The linear relationship extends to the glucose concentration as high as 20mM, which is higher than 15mM typically for the detection of blood glucose in practice [52]. Furthermore, the amperometric response was found to be about ten orders of magnitude higher than that of more conventional flat electrodes coated with glucose oxidase-containing polypyrrole films under the same conditions [52].

Apart from the large surface/interface area obtained for the nanotube-supported conducting polymer layer, which is attractive for using them in sensing applications, the coaxial structure allows the nanotube framework to provide mechanical stability [53, 54] and efficient thermal/electrical conduction [55, 56, 57] to and from the conducting polymer layer. Furthermore, the CP-CNT nanowire sensors were also demonstrated to be highly selective for glucose with their amperometric responses being almost unchanged even in the presence of some interference species including ascorbic acid, urea, and D-fructose. Therefore, the CP-CNT nanowires could be used for making new glucose sensors with a high sensitivity, selectivity, and reliability, which is clearly an area in which future work would be of value.

Figure 5. The dependence of electrooxidation current at the oxidative potential of H_2O_2 on the glucose concentration for the CP-NT coaxial nanowire sensor (solid squares) and the conventional polypyrrole sensor on a flat electrode under the same conditions (open circles) [51].

4. CONCLUSION

We have demonstrated that aligned carbon nanotubes are ideal materials for many potential applications. They also served as excellent substrates for making novel polymer and nanotube composites. The polymer and aligned carbon nanotube nanocomposites are particularly attractive for a large variety of device applications, ranging from the improved electron emitters to highly sensitive biosensors. With so many advanced surface functionalization and device fabrication methods already reported and more to be developed, the examples discussed in this paper will surely be only the first few of many nanocomposite systems based on polymers and aligned carbon nanotubes attractive for potential applications.

5. REFERENCES

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